

Research Article

The Formulation and Characterization Of Liposomes Of Thiocolchicoside & Effect On Against Inflammation

Suman Kumari, Dr. Sachin Kumar*, Ravi Jayant

Department of Pharmaceutics, NKBR College of Pharmacy & Research Centre, Meerut U.P.

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 08 July 2024
Accepted: 23 July 2024
Published: 26 July 2024

Keywords:

Inflammation, Liposome,
Drug delivery system, Stearic
acid, Soya

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.12890241

ABSTRACT

Thiocolchicoside, an FDA-approved drug, serves as an anti-inflammatory and muscle relaxant for orthopedic, traumatic, and rheumatologic disorders. Despite the efficacy of conventional formulations like capsules, these are linked to rapid drug release and frequent dosing, along with an unpalatable bitter taste, rendering them unsuitable for tablet forms. Controlled release oral formulations of thiocolchicoside can mitigate these issues by prolonging drug release, reducing dosing frequency, enhancing patient compliance, and improving bioavailability. Liposome encapsulation, leveraging their biodegradable and biocompatible properties, presents a viable solution for these challenges. Material & Method: This study utilized the thin film hydration method to fabricate thiocolchicoside liposomes using soya lecithin, cholesterol, and organic solvents, chosen for their cost-effectiveness and availability. Evaluations included visual appeal, yield percentage, particle size, zeta potential, micromeritic properties, drug content, encapsulation efficiency, in vitro drug release, release kinetics, and stability. Result: Liposomes produced exhibited favorable characteristics, with yields from 93.1% to 98.8%, particle sizes between 2042.1 to 2158.4 μm , and zeta potentials from -43.5 to 47.2 mV. The encapsulation efficiency and drug content ranged from 89.6% to 93.7% and 81.35% to 87.72%, respectively. Formulation LT6, with the highest encapsulation efficiency, demonstrated optimal performance. Stability and release kinetics studies affirmed the robustness of LT6, showing no significant changes over three months under stress conditions. The Korsmeyer-Peppas model best described the drug release kinetics, indicating non-Fickian diffusion. Overall, thiocolchicoside-loaded liposomes significantly enhance drug release control, dosing frequency reduction, and patient compliance.

INTRODUCTION

Generally speaking, inflammation happens when pathogenic microbes like bacteria, viruses, or

fungi enter the body, settle in certain tissues, or move through the bloodstream.[1] Other mechanisms that might cause inflammation

*Corresponding Author: Dr. Sachin Kumar

Address: Assistant Professor, Dr. Rajendra Gode College of Pharmacy, Amravati, Maharashtra- 444901

Email ✉: sachin.mpharm86@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

include tissue damage, malignancy, ischemia, degeneration, & cell death. The genesis of inflammation is mostly attributed to both the innate and adaptive immune responses.[2] The primary defensive mechanism against invasive microbes and cancerous cells is the innate immune system, which is composed of a variety of cells such as mast cells, dendritic cells, and macrophages.[3] More specialized cells called B and T cells work with the adaptive immune system to produce certain receptors and antibodies that destroy cancer cells and invasive infections.[4] Liposomes are spherical fat (lipid) based nanocarriers used in targeted drug delivery encapsulated with bioactive compounds [5] Particles in liposomes that range in size around 50 to 500 μ and are made up of one or more lipid bilayers, that contain API in dissolved or dispersed form and phospholipid layer as external layer for stabilization [6].

Liposomes have attained attention these days for its stability, biocompatibility, ease of synthesis, higher bioavailability, higher drug loading efficiency, controlled drug release and for its effectiveness in protecting the drug or active moiety from hydrolysis. So far, the Liposomes have been used for several drug candidates that include anti-inflammatory, anesthetics, anti-bacterial and anti-cancer agents for its controlled drug release property ([7] [8], [9]).

Mechanism of drug release:

Three main processes underlie the action of liposomes: diffusion, degradation, and swelling.

Diffusion: Diffusion is the method by which the medicine is released via the pores in the polymer matrix that surrounds the core substance. When a polymers layer develops over the core material, the drug / active component is released in a regulated manner [10]

Degradation: In some cases, the polymer and API are mixed together uniformly to form matrix system. Through the polymeric layer, the

medication diffuses into the surrounding environment and is released from the matrix system. The drug releases from the matrix system at a slower rate when it takes longer for it to move from the inner core to the outside world [11].

Swelling: Normally dry, the controlled release systems become wet when they come into touch with bodily fluids or liquids, the polymers present in coating material swells and enables the core material or drug to diffuse through the swollen polymeric material that form pores on its layer during swelling. This allows the release of the drug from the swollen material to external environment.

MATERIAL & METHOD:

Preformulation Studies

A major part of formulation of new formulation is pre-formulation. These studies concentrate on the characteristics of the medication that may have an impact on its effectiveness and the creation of an effective dosage form. By using different analytical methods like IR spectroscopy, UV spectroscopy, melting point, etc., the drug sample that was obtained was identified.

Physical Appearance

The active material Thiocolchicoside purchased from supplier was observed for its physical appearance.

Melting Point

The capillary fusion technique was used to determine the melting point. Thiocolchicoside, in a minute amount, was fed into a capillary from a melting point device. The drug starts to melt and the temperature was noted on which the solid drug turned into liquid [12].

FTIR

An FTIR spectrum for pure drug was obtained by adding 1-2 mg of drug sample in the suitable holder in FTIR chamber. Fourier-transform infrared spectrum was measured in the scanning range of 400 to 4000 cm^{-1} [13].

Partition Coefficient

The 10 mg of Clopidogrel bisulphate was weighed and taken in the stoppered vials already containing 10 mL of n-octanol and water. The vials were shaken for 24 h or until the two phases separated and collected in separating funnel which was analyzed by spectrophotometric method. The drug concentration in water divided by the drug concentration in n-octanol is the partition coefficient (P.C.) [12]

UV- Visible Spectroscopy Preparation of Calibration Curve Of Thiocolchicoside

A 100 ml standard flask was used to dilute a precisely measured quantity of medication (100 mg) with methanol until it reached the mark. After diluting the sample by a factor of 100, it was scanned in the ultraviolet (UV) range of 200 to 400 nm. At 248 nm, the absorbance was found to be at its peak. Transferring 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1, and 1.4 ml from the solution to a 10 ml standard flask was the next step. Using a UV spectrophotometer, the absorbance was measured at 248 nm. The range of medication concentrations from 2 to 14 μ g/ml was used to study the linearity Dixit et al. (2022).

Solubility Studies

The solubility of the medicine was tested by dissolving 10 mg of the drug in various solvents and shaking the mixture for 30 minutes in a water bath shaker. The solvents used were water, alcohol (methanol, ethanol), 0.1N hydrochloric acid, ABS (pH 4.5), PBS (pH 6.8), and pH 7.4. Visual examination was used to examine the solubility. For quantitative solubility, 10 mg Thiocolchicoside was taken in test tube. 10 mL of different solvents were added and closed tightly and shaken for 24hrs. The drug was determined at $\lambda_{\max}$ 248 nm Patel et al. (2013).

Drug Excipient Compatibility Studies

FTIR Spectrometric Studies: Fourier Transform Infrared

Soy Lecithin and Cholesterol (an excipient) were analyzed in an FTIR spectra by placing 1-2 mg of

the sample in the appropriate holder inside the FTIR chamber. The Fourier-transform infrared spectra were recorded within the 400–4000 cm^{-1} scanning range. Similar study was conducted for Thiocolchicoside and excipient combination [14]

Preparation of Liposomes

Liposomes loaded with Thiocolchicoside were prepared using Thin Film Hydration method. Thiocolchicoside, Soy lecithin and cholesterol in varied concentrations were dissolved in mixture of Chloroform and methanol in the ratio of 9:1. This solution was taken in a round bottom flask and kept on a rota evaporator at 60°C for 15 minutes on 90 rpm. This evaporated the chloroform leaving behind a thin layer of lipids. This thin layer of lipids was also dried further for 15 minutes to obtain dry residue. The organic solvent was completely dried by vacuum overnight to obtain film. This film was then hydrated with phosphate buffer 7.4 by vortexing for 10 minutes and then hydrated for 60 minutes at 70°C on 90rpm. The formed liposomal suspension is centrifuged by ultra-centrifugation at 3000 rpm for half an hour to obtain liposomes [15][16].

Characterization Of Liposomes

Appearance

The prepared Liposomes were visually checked for its color and surface texture (Roy et al. 2018).

Percentage Yield

State that the yield of the formulations was calculated by dividing the formulation's end weight by the drug & an excipient begin weights. state that the yield of the formulations was calculated by dividing the formulation's end weight by the drug & the excipient begin weight.[17]

Particle Size

Using the dynamic light scattering method, we were able to measure the size of the nanoparticles. recommended diluting all samples ten times with

distilled water prior to testing for optimal signal strength.

Zeta Potential

Zeta potential was measured employing Zetasizer. [18] presented the findings of diluting the nanoparticles with distilled water and putting them in a zeta cell.

Micromeritic Properties

- a. **Angle of repose:** The angle of repose was calculated by dividing the pile height (as a function of pile radius) by the pile radius created by liposomes. The value less than 25 indicates excellent flow properties of formulated liposomes.
- b. **Bulk density:** The mass of solid lipid nanoparticles (M) and their bulk volume (V_b) in a measuring cylinder were divided to get the bulk density (ρ_b). The unit for bulk density is gm/cm^3 .
- c. **Tapped Density:** The tap density (ρ_t) is determined by dividing the mass (M) of liposomes by their tap volume (V_t), that is obtained via a tap density device. Tapped density is measured in gm/cm^3 .
- d. **Compressibility index:** A Carr's index or under 10 percent indicates an exceptional flow of liposomes. The Carr's index (I) is measured using the formula:

$$I = [(V_t - V_b) / V_t] \times 100$$
- e. **Hausner ratio:** The tapped density (ρ_t) and bulk density (ρ_b) of the liposomes that were created are divided to get the Hausner ratio. The Hausner's ratio must be between 1-1.1 for excellent flow of liposomes [19].

Drug Content

A 100 ml volumetric flask was used to hold the ground, weighed, and SLN formulations, each of which contained 100 mg. Before being filled to the mark with PBS (pH 7.4), the flask was shaken. "The drug content was determined by analyzing

the absorbance of the diluted solution at 248 nm using UV spectroscopy after the solution was further diluted to a concentration of $10\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ [20].

Encapsulation Efficiency

We used the following formula to determine the liposome encapsulating efficiency:

$$\text{Encapsulation Efficiency} = \frac{\text{Estimated \% Drug Content}}{\text{Theoretical \% Drug Content}} \times 100$$

In Vitro Drug Release Studies

USP Dissolution Testing Apparatus II was used to find out how quickly the produced formulations released their contents. A phosphate buffer solution with a pH of 7.4 was used in the dissolving tests, which was carried out at a temperature of $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ and a speed of 50 rpm. Using a UV spectrophotometer, we measured the percentage of drug release after withdrawing 5 ml of sample every 2 minutes for up to 20 minutes and replacing it with new medium to keep the sink condition constant [21]

RESULT

Preformulation studies:

Thiocolchicoside is white crystalline powder form with no order. And its melt on 192°C temperature.

UV Analysis:

The drug (0.01% w/v) in methanol was scanned between 200–400 nm and absorption maxima was determined spectrophotometrically. It exhibited absorption maxima at 248 nm. The method estimated the drug concentration in methanol followed the Beer's Lambert law in the concentration ranges ($2.0\text{--}14\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$) at 248 nm (**Figure 1.1,1.2**). The regression equation for Thiocolchicoside, as represented by the standard curve in the graph, is $y = 0.064x - 0.007$, and the R^2 value is 0.981, which, indicates good linearity. The estimation procedure was found to be fairly reproducible, convenient, inexpensive and sensitive.

Figure 1.1 UV graph of Thiocolchicoside

Figure 1.2 Calibration data of Thiocolchicoside

Solubility Study:

The solubility was checked in different mediums for Thiocolchicoside which was found to be soluble in water. The amount of the drug dissolved was analyzed spectrophotometrically using UV Visible spectrophotometer and the

solubility (mg) was represented in **Figure 1.3**. The solubility of the Thiocolchicoside was found to be in the following order:

pH 6.8 Phosphate buffer < pH 7.4 Phosphate buffer < pH 4.5 Acetate Buffer < Ethanol < Water < 0.1N HCl < Methanol

Figure 1.3 Solubility of Thiocolchicoside in various solvents

Drug excipient compatibility studies:

The FTIR of excipient and pure drug was done and the FTIR of drug and excipient mixture was done (Figure 1.4-1.5) and few additional IR peaks

were observed. Although, this didn't have any interference with the major peaks of drug and can be further used for fabrication.

Figure 1.4 FTIR spectra of Stearic acid

Figure 1.5 FTIR spectra of Soy Lecithin

Figure 1.6 FTIR spectra of drug and excipient mixture

Preparation of Liposomes

The liposomes were prepared by thin film hydration method using varied concentrations of stearic acid and Soy Lecithin. This method was chosen because this method has ease of fabrication, is straightforward and repeatable.

Characterization of Liposomes

Appearance

The prepared liposomes were visually checked for its color and surface texture. The results are depicted in figure no. 1.7 and illustrated stable, white liposomes with slightly smooth texture

Percentage Yield

Figure no 1.7 Percentage yield

Particle size

The dynamic light scattering method, which is shown in Figure 1.8 and Table 1.1 was used to measure the liposomes' particle size. When soy lecithin content was raised, liposome size of particles increased. Particle sizes for each

formulation ranged from 2042.1 μm to 2158.4 μm .

Table no 1.1 Particle size of Thiocolchicoside Liposomes (LT 1 - LT 6)

S. No.	Formulation	Particle size (μm)
1	LT 1	2042.1 $\pm$ 0.2
2	LT 2	2046.6 $\pm$ 0.4
3	LT 3	2045.9 $\pm$ 0.5
4	LT 4	2157.2 $\pm$ 0.8
5	LT 5	2158.4 $\pm$ 0.66
6	LT 6	2157.9 $\pm$ 0.47

Zeta Potential

The zeta potential of Liposomes was determined using Zetasizer and the results were found in the range of -43.5 to -47.2 mV. The zeta potential of all formulations comprising from LT 1 to LT 6 are depicted in Figure 1.8 to Figure 1.13

Figure 1.8 Zeta Potential of Thiocolchicoside LT 1

Figure 1.9 Zeta Potential of Thiocolchicoside LT 2

Figure 1.12 Zeta Potential of Thiocolchicoside LT 5

Figure 1.10 Zeta Potential of Thiocolchicoside LT 3

Figure 1.13 Zeta Potential of Thiocolchicoside LT 6

Figure 1.11 Zeta Potential of Thiocolchicoside LT 4

Encapsulation Efficiency

The Encapsulation efficiency (E.E.) of liposomes was calculated and was found to be in the range of 89.6 to 93.7%. The formulation LT 6 showed table no 1.2 highest drug encapsulation efficiency

Table no.1.2 encapsulation efficiency

Formulation	Drug Encapsulation Efficiency (%)
LT 1	89.6 ± 0.5
LT 2	89.9 ± 0.1
LT 3	90.1 ± 0.5
LT 4	92.7 ± 0.1
LT 5	93.1 ± 0.4
LT 6	93.7 ± 0.8

In vitro Drug Release Studies

The release rate of drug loaded Liposomes was determined using USP dissolution testing

apparatus II (Electro lab, India). The *in vitro* release data are shown in the graphical representation is Figure 1.14. The cumulative percentage drug release from Liposomes prepared with higher concentration of Soy lecithin showed slower drug release when compared to lower amount of phospholipid. Higher concentration of soy lecithin leads to slower drug release and the rate of drug release is found to be in the order $LT\ 6 < LT\ 5 < LT\ 4 < LT\ 3 < LT\ 2 < LT\ 1$.

Figure 1.14 in-vitro drug release

CONCLUSION

Thiocolchicoside, an FDA-approved anti-inflammatory drug, is used in treatment of orthopaedic, traumatic, and rheumatologic disorders. Conventional oral formulations are effective but have rapid drug release and high dosing frequencies. To improve drug release, controlled release oral formulations are needed. Liposomes, a biodegradable and biocompatible material, have gained attention for their low toxicity and low cost. A study used a thin film hydration method to create Thiocolchicoside liposomes using soya lecithin, cholesterol, and organic solvent. The liposomes showed a range of drug content and encapsulation effectiveness, with the most effective formulation being LT 6. Stability tests and drug release kinetics were conducted on LT6, and the Korsmeyer Peppas release kinetics were found to be most appropriate for drug-loaded liposomes. Liposomes are crucial for maintaining medication release, decreasing dosage frequency, and improving patient compliance.

REFERENCE

1. H. Ramos Abellán, C. Hernandez, R. Simó Canonge, and O. Simó-Servat, "Inflammation: The Link between Neural and Vascular Impairment in the Diabetic Retina and Therapeutic Implications," 2023.
2. L. Chen et al., "Inflammatory responses and inflammation-associated diseases in organs," *Oncotarget*, vol. 9, no. 6, p. 7204, 2018.
3. M. Raslan, M. S. Eslam, A. R. Sara, and N. A. Sabri, "Immune System response to COVID-19. An endless story," *Acta Sci. Pharm. Sci.* (ISSN 2581-5423), vol. 6, no. 6, 2022.
4. D. D. Chaplin, "Overview of the immune response," *J. Allergy Clin. Immunol.*, vol. 125, no. 2, pp. S3–S23, 2010.
5. H. Nsairat, D. Khater, U. Sayed, F. Odeh, A. Al Bawab, and W. Alshaer, "Liposomes: Structure, composition, types, and clinical applications," *Heliyon*, vol. 8, no. 5, 2022.
6. A. Akbarzadeh et al., "Liposome: classification, preparation, and applications," *Nanoscale Res. Lett.*, vol. 8, pp. 1–9, 2013.
7. D. J. McClements and J. Rao, "Food-grade nanoemulsions: formulation, fabrication, properties, performance, biological fate, and potential toxicity," *Crit. Rev. Food Sci. Nutr.*, vol. 51, no. 4, pp. 285–330, 2011.
8. G. T. Noble, J. F. Stefanick, J. D. Ashley, T. Kiziltepe, and B. Bilgicer, "Ligand-targeted liposome design: challenges and fundamental considerations," *Trends Biotechnol.*, vol. 32, no. 1, pp. 32–45, 2014.
9. S. Gerstberger, M. Hafner, and T. Tuschl, "A census of human RNA-binding proteins," *Nat. Rev. Genet.*, vol. 15, no. 12, pp. 829–845, 2014.
10. Z. Wang and R. A. Shmeis, "Dissolution controlled drug delivery systems," *Des. Control. release drug Deliv. Syst.* United States McGraw-Hill, pp. 139–172, 2006.

11. J. Siepmann and F. Siepmann, "Modeling of diffusion controlled drug delivery," *J. Control. release*, vol. 161, no. 2, pp. 351–362, 2012.
12. J. Patel, L. Němcová, P. Maguire, W. G. Graham, and D. Mariotti, "Synthesis of surfactant-free electrostatically stabilized gold nanoparticles by plasma-induced liquid chemistry," *Nanotechnology*, vol. 24, no. 24, p. 245604, 2013.
13. M. Kulkarni et al., "Titanium nanostructures for biomedical applications," *Nanotechnology*, vol. 26, no. 6, p. 62002, 2015.
14. Y. Wang et al., "Super-natural instructions: Generalization via declarative instructions on 1600+ nlp tasks," *arXiv Prepr. arXiv2204.07705*, 2022.
15. S. Ramasamy Ramamurthy and N. Roy, "Recent trends in machine learning for human activity recognition—A survey," *Wiley Interdiscip. Rev. Data Min. Knowl. Discov.*, vol. 8, no. 4, p. e1254, 2018.
16. K. F. Rabe et al., "Efficacy and safety of dupilumab in glucocorticoid-dependent severe asthma," *N. Engl. J. Med.*, vol. 378, no. 26, pp. 2475–2485, 2018.
17. R. Trivedi et al., "Effects of Egb 761 on bone mineral density, bone microstructure, and osteoblast function: possible roles of quercetin and kaempferol," *Mol. Cell. Endocrinol.*, vol. 302, no. 1, pp. 86–91, 2009.
18. S. Lankalapalli, V. Tenneti, and S. K. Nimmali, "Design and development of vancomycin liposomes," *Indian J. Pharm. Educ. Res.*, vol. 49, pp. 208–215, 2015.
19. R. Rathi, S. Kaur, and I. Singh, "A review on co-crystals of Herbal Bioactives for solubility enhancement: preparation methods and characterization techniques," *Cryst. Growth Des.*, vol. 22, no. 3, pp. 2023–2042, 2022.
20. U. S. Shivhare, M. Gupta, S. Basu, and G. S. V Raghavan, "Optimization of blanching process for carrots," *J. Food Process Eng.*, vol. 32, no. 4, pp. 587–605, 2009.
21. R. Roy, M. Tiwari, G. Donelli, and V. Tiwari, "Strategies for combating bacterial biofilms: A focus on anti-biofilm agents and their mechanisms of action," *Virulence*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 522–554, 2018.

HOW TO CITE: Suman Kumari, Dr. Sachin kumar*, Ravi Jayant, The Formulation and Characterization Of Liposomes Of Thiocolchicoside & Effect On Against Inflammation, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2024, Vol 2, Issue 7, 1868-1877. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12890241>